

POLICY BRIEFS

Informing EU Forest Policy: Recommendations for a Cohesive and Future-Proof Approach For The Forestry and Agroforestry World

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Transversal
Policy
Briefs

EIP Agri funding can drive innovation in forestry and agroforestry. Supportive administrations and longer project cycles are key

Why interactive innovation across countries matters for forestry and agroforestry in Europe?

Forests and agroforestry systems account for almost 45% of the land in the EU and provide a wide range of ecosystem services, including natural habitats, water regulation, carbon storage and sequestration, wood and non-wood products. Together, they have great potential to facilitate the ambition of a sustainable green transition in Europe yet face significant challenges such as fragmented forest ownership, land abandonment and demographic decline in rural areas. Innovations are key to revitalize and improve long-standing practices, but need to be promoted by knowledge transfer, co-creation of digital solutions for increased efficiency in operations and monitoring of ecosystem services, and development of business models with products from forestry and agroforestry.

FOREST4EU research shows that OG innovators in forestry and agroforestry would recommend participating in the interactive and multi-stakeholder-driven approach proposed by the European Innovation Partnerships (EIP-Agri) of the CAP Network. Yet, the share of forestry and agroforestry projects share is limited, representing only 7%. To enhance uptake and unleash the full potential of forestry and agroforestry for green growth and societal well-being in Europe, administrative and project management barriers must be tackled.

Figure 1: How OG members in forestry and agroforestry look at EIP-AGRI funding (results from FOREST4EU survey research, n = 73)

Who can act and how

Forest owners and managers, farmers and research organization drive partnerships for innovation in forestry and agroforestry. To thrive in collaboration, succeed in implementing their novel solutions and approaches, and create impact, innovators in forestry and agroforestry need supportive government authorities, advisors, and associations.

The EIP-Agri Operational Groups are multi-actor driven innovation partnerships that pull complementary knowledge and expertise together and operate from bottom-up. Their operation at national and regional levels, requires that government authorities create user-friendly and easily accessible rules for project design, selection procedures, eligibility of costs, accounting and reporting, and payment of approved funding.

Advisors acting as innovation brokers and project coordinators are key to guide the thorough preparation process, development and implementation of work plans and resolution of financial or organizational issues.

Policymakers in ministries, involved in rural development programming and CAP strategic plans determine funding streams and thus play very important roles in funding for forestry and agroforestry. Policymakers can include topical issues of the forest sector into calls for funding applications, ensure their effective communication, and steer how the different government authorities involved in the administration of EIP-Agri funding collaborate.

National networks for rural development can facilitate the networking of Operational Groups and disseminate the concrete solutions found and implemented through various media and at events. Their accumulated expertise is also salient for policymaking at EU level where decisions about the future of the CAP Network are taken. The national networks can help communicating administrative concerns from local level to the EU level.

Policy recommendations

FOREST4EU offers several recommendations how to improve the enabling environment for interactive innovation in forestry and agroforestry by means of EIP-Agri.

The complex administration and market pressure hamper potential beneficiaries to invest resources in applications for EIP-Agri funding. A less burdensome and more efficient project planning and implementation is highly recommended. This can be done through pre-payments and budget adaptability, as well as administrative simplification and regional policies that put innovation and entrepreneurship at the centre.

KEY CHALLENGES IN FORESTRY AND AGROFORESTRY

LONGER FUNDING CYCLES

Current **funding** cycles often **might not** match the long-term nature of forestry and production **projects**.

BUREAUCRACY VS. MARKET SPEED

Slow bureaucratic **processes** often **fail to keep pace** with and capitalize on fast-moving market **opportunities**, thereby **hindering** market **growth** and development.

IMPORTANCE OF PROJECT EVALUATION

Evaluate project achievements to establish **credibility** and a **strong role**.

Forestry and agroforestry operate both in short and longer-time horizons. Extending the lifetime of funding projects would allow for thorough knowledge transfer and training within such longer project timelines, helping new practices take root and continue beyond the project's end. The Operational Groups working in this area require longer funding cycles than the standard project duration of 3 years to fully test and scale innovations and ensure knowledge transfer.

The outputs and impacts of innovation projects merit adequate evaluation to learn from practice how to develop forestry and agroforestry into the future. Focusing on the new tools or approaches as means to adjust to changing conditions (economic, social, climatic, etc.), and involving forest owners and farmers increase the validity of the evaluations. Cross-country study visits help to draw lessons learned from innovation practice and multiply the dissemination.

Conclusions

Interactive innovation in forestry and agroforestry is successful if:

It creates ownership and commitment from multiple stakeholders in innovation including innovators in forestry and agroforestry, administrations, associations, and networks for rural development.

It facilitates knowledge transfer and new solutions at regional, national, and transnational levels.

It promotes agroforestry across Europe to improve adaptation to climate change and helps sustaining farmers' income.

It operates with longer project timelines, helping new practices take root and continue beyond the project's end

It improves management, adaptive capacity, and sustainability to create impact for green growth and well-being.

Policy briefs on
“Wood mobilization”

The role of wood mobilisation in building a sustainable forest bioeconomy

Why innovations matter for the mobilization of wood?

The forest-wood value chain reduces European dependency on fossil materials, supports the bioeconomy, and revitalizes rural areas. However, wood mobilization remains a limited factor in many EU regions, influenced by a combination of: fragmented forest ownership; inadequate infrastructure; low economic viability of harvesting operations; administrative burdens and lack of coordination among actors.

Innovations developed through EIP-Agri Operational Groups (OGs) have demonstrated that digital solutions, cooperative structures, and tailored advisory services can unlock the potential of dormant forest resources while contributing to the green transition in many regions.

Who can do what?

EU and National Policymakers can incentivise cooperation among businesses to ensure sustainable supply and increase efficiency across the forest-based value chain. This can be done by providing grants or tax breaks to encourage partnerships between forest owners, processors, and timber buyers. Supporting the digitalization of the forestry sector for management, monitoring, and marketing is key. Authorities that simplify administrative procedures (such as permitting and subsidy applications) promote active forest management.

Regional and Local Authorities can facilitate wood mobilization by investing in infrastructure including forest roads or local processing facilities to make the harvesting and transport of timber more efficient. These authorities are uniquely positioned to catalyse regional collaboration with multi-stakeholder platforms and alliances that unite forest owners, logging companies, sawmills, and other actors to co-design local solutions for wood mobilization.

Moreover, regional and local bodies can support demonstration projects that pilot innovative approaches and real-life examples of sustainable wood harvesting and utilization, as such approaches can accelerate the adoption of best practices in their communities.

Forest Owners and Managers are the operational heart of wood mobilization. They can increase their impact and efficiency by through cooperative management and marketing initiatives. Embracing modern digital tools (forest management software, online timber marketplaces, and remote sensing technologies) can help owners and managers to plan harvests better, monitor forest health, and connect with buyers more easily. Additionally, actively engaging in training programs through workshops, forestry extension services, or peer learning allows forest owners and managers to stay up-to-date on sustainable silvicultural techniques and new technologies.

Research and Innovation Actors can collaborate closely with practitioners in the forest sector to co-develop practical solutions including decision-support systems or harvesting equipment helping the wood mobilization sector to move forward. They can also make their research outcomes more accessible and easier to apply. Research and Innovation actors also help bridge the gap between innovation and practice through capacity building.

Private Sector can develop and refine business models that make sustainable forest management and wood supply economically attractive and promote awareness about the benefits of active and sustainable wood use. Moreover, businesses and training institutions can also offer regular training workshops for forest owners on how to use a new mobile app and provide helplines for troubleshooting.

Policy implications

The successful implementation of wood mobilization strategies rely heavily on a supportive policy environment. The Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) and the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) should explicitly target wood mobilization as a strategic objective, providing dedicated funding and support instruments. In parallel, EU frameworks should both invest in forest infrastructure and formally recognize digital tools and decision-support systems as valuable instruments in sustainable forest management. Promoting shared forest management models such as cooperatives or joint planning mechanisms, which can help activate smallholders and optimize resource accessibility as well as resource use.

Conclusions

Mobilizing wood sustainably is not just a technical challenge – it’s a governance opportunity. With the right policy support, wood mobilization can become a driver for innovations across the forest-based value chain, rural development, and ecological resilience. To improve forest resilience forests must be activated – not abandoned.

Policy briefs on
“Forest adaptation to
climate change”

Adjustment of silvicultural practices, adoption of new technologies and dissemination drive innovations for forest adaptation to climate change in Europe

Why innovations matter for adaptation to climate change in forestry?

Forests play a key role in many European policies helping to mitigate the effects of climate change. With increasing natural disturbances, adaptation to climate change has become an essential element to increase forests' resilience. In fact, according to FOREST4EU results, climate change is the major driver of innovation across Europe favoring the development of new technologies, products, and services. Innovations for adaptation to climate change in forestry promote the adjustment of silvicultural practices with use of new technologies (decision support tools and remote sensing), based on better and faster knowledge dissemination, and new forms of collaboration. Key innovation themes emerging from Operational Groups (OGs) working on climate change adaptation include adaptive forestry practices, the integration of cutting-edge technologies and development of decision-support tools, and robust strategies for knowledge transfer, stakeholder awareness, and effective communication.

Figure 1: Types of innovation for adaptation to climate change in forestry

Who can do what?

EU and National policy makers, in agreement with regional and local authorities, can create enabling frameworks that support participatory governance, fostering transparency and better and faster dissemination of solutions.

The EU CAP network can share knowledge and information about agriculture, forest and rural policy. It would be relevant to mobilize the focus groups, created ad hoc, with the participation of around 20 experts each through Europe, to build upon their expertise in the forest and agroforestry sector and their potentialities to adapt to climate change based on the most recent data and knowledge available.

At operational level, forest owners and managers should be involved by research organizations to co-create innovative solutions ensuring transferability and adoption of the new practices.

Policy implications

Innovative adaptive forestry requires support for long-term R&D projects to properly analyse the results of experiments. Their follow-up will help produce technical guidelines for operations. Harmonisation of protocols at European level and standardisation of methods and data collection, between public and private forests are necessary to encourage collaboration and improve the precision and replicability of results. The high demand for new technologies, decision support tools and remote sensing data require specialized knowledge. Under well-controlled conditions, the use of AI can contribute to the development of new decision-making tools. Integrative platforms that combine different tools and data are needed to facilitate and accelerate administrative procedures, as well as decision making, and to develop more accessible and user-friendly applications. Even once widely disseminated, the best knowledge and practices still need to be adopted by end users. Forest advisors and other stakeholders must create and maintain relationships of trust which requires ongoing support and animation through extension activities.

Conclusions

Adapting forests to climate change must become Europe's top priority to safeguard their vital functions such as wood production, carbon storage, water regulation, and biodiversity on which we base our survival and well-being. Emphasis should be placed on supporting forest owners and decision-makers in the evolution of their practices.

Innovative climate change adaptation in forestry highlights the importance of adaptive practices, field experimentation, advanced technologies, decision-support tools, and effective communication as key drivers of resilience. There is a strong demand for new technologies and decision support tools, in particular remote sensing data, and for administrative simplifications by the means of automatic incorporation of results from those tools. Developing long-term R&D projects and networks with harmonized protocols and stable funding at EU level are crucial to obtain reliable and comparable results for all member states.

Policy briefs on
“Sustainable forest
management and
ecosystem services”

Innovating Forest Management and Silviculture: Enhancing All Ecosystem Services through Local and EU Policies

Why innovations matter for ecosystem services in forest management

Europe’s forests are central to **climate mitigation**, **biodiversity conservation**, **support of rural economies**, and **human wellbeing**. They provide an array of ecosystem services (FES) often not traded on markets. At present, **carbon sequestration** is the only ecosystem service with a formal market, while biodiversity and other services remain excluded, creating a major disincentive for managing forests in multifunctional ways. Innovations are salient to incentivize forest owners to manage their forests in an integral way by creating credible and transparent markets for various ecosystem services, supporting the design of digital monitoring systems (such as UAVs, LiDAR, and decision-support platforms), and providing adaptive silvicultural tools. In the context of highly fragmented forest ownership, digital tools that reduce management costs are indispensable. However, these tools must be tailored to the real needs of forest managers and owners, and in line with forest legislation, to respond effectively to practical challenges. Moreover, innovations are also essential for improving the safety, and attractiveness of forest work, as well as for strengthening policy integration across sectors that often operate in silos

Who can act and how

The responsibility for innovation adoption lies across multiple levels. EU and national policy makers can create enabling frameworks that reward ecosystem services, also essential for adaptive silviculture, especially closer-to-nature models that prioritize resilience and biodiversity conservation.

Regional and local authorities play a role in deploying digital platforms, supporting participatory governance, and fostering transparency. At the operational level, forest owners and managers can adopt adaptive management. Research and academia along with practitioners can co-develop innovations ensuring transferability, while updating forestry education to address new challenges. Finally, the private sector and NGOs can accelerate the scaling of digital solutions, innovative business models, and awareness-raising activities.

Policy implications

Innovation cannot succeed without policy coherence: contradictions between energy, biodiversity, and forest policies undermine credibility and hamper multifunctional forest management.

- Carbon and biodiversity credit markets must be created and standardized in a way that ensures transparency, EU-wide harmonization, and future expansion to other ecosystem services.
- Equally important is the recognition and adoption of digital tools, as official monitoring instruments in European governance.
- Local incentives that foster collaboration among actors, such as Operational Groups where forest owners, practitioners, and researchers from the same region work together, are key to generating effective and practical innovations.
- Participatory approaches should be incentivized to strengthen legitimacy and reduce conflicts among stakeholders. Finally, modern education and training systems are needed to ensure a skilled workforce capable of adopting new practices safely and effectively.

Europe’s forests face increasing risks from climate change, disturbances, and fragmentation. Innovations in the sector can help forests become powerful allies in achieving EU climate goals securing carbon storage capacity, protecting biodiversity, and revitalizing local economies.

Innovations for sustainable forest management are no longer about balancing wood production and conservation. Instead, a multidisciplinary and participatory paradigm is required where digital technologies, adaptive silviculture, and governance reforms converge to secure the constant provision of multiple ecosystem services.

The message is clear:

“ Forestry innovations are not optional. They are essential for resilient forests that provide multiple ecosystem services for future generations. ”

Conclusions

Providing financial incentives to forest owners for multiple ecosystem services can promote closer-to-nature silviculture. **Digital platforms** for data extraction and monitoring play a critical role in this process as they enable precise mapping of forest resources and ecosystem services, allow integration of local and regional data for monitoring, certification, and policy compliance, support adaptive management and decision-making and allow integration of local and regional data for monitoring, certification, and policy compliance reduce costs and improve transparency for forest managers and owners.

Policy briefs on
“Non-wood forest products”

Innovations in Non-Wood Forest Products are vital to fully embed them in the bioeconomy, boosting rural development and human well-being

Why Innovations Matter for Non-Wood Forest Products (NWFPs)

Non-wood forest products (NWFPs) such as cork, resins, mushrooms, truffles, nuts, berries, and medicinal plants play a key role in the maintenance of rural livelihoods, cultural heritage, sustainable food systems, and the green economy. They contribute to climate action, biodiversity conservation, rural employment, and healthier diets. Despite generating up to €23 billion annually in Europe, NWFP value chains remain underdeveloped due to fragmented policies, scarce and unreliable production and market data, informal markets, and lack of innovation. This gap highlights the need to place them more firmly on the policy and innovation agenda.

Latest data of EIP-AGRI Operational Groups show that innovations in NWFPs play a key role as they:

- Focus on products, processes, and services, with strong emphasis on technological advancements;
- Contribute to social equity and rural development, although innovations in social and organizational dimensions remain limited;
- Increase sustainability and transparency in production and harvesting;
- Develop competitive, territorial, and fair value chains;
- Foster product differentiation through certification, traceability, and quality standards;
- Link science, practice, and policy.

Who can do what?

EU institutions: The European Union has a central role in setting the framework conditions for NWFP innovation. It should ensure policy coherence across agriculture, forestry, and industrial strategies so that NWFPs are not treated as marginal by-products but as integral resources within the bioeconomy. Strengthening support to thematic networks and knowledge-exchange platforms helps innovations circulate more quickly across Member States. Moreover, EU institutions can provide long-term and stable funding to high-performing innovation groups, ensuring that promising pilot initiatives have the resources and time to mature into consolidated NWFP value chains.

National and regional authorities: At the territorial level, governments can shape an enabling environment for NWFP producers. This means designing fiscal and labor regimes that recognize the seasonality of many NWFP activities and provide protections against informal or undeclared work.

Authorities can also play a key role in establishing price observatories, thereby increasing transparency and trust in markets. Finally, they can promote certification and labeling schemes linked to origin, sustainability, and quality, helping local products gain visibility and competitiveness in both domestic and international markets.

Research and innovation networks: Knowledge institutions should advance research not only on new technologies but also on the scalability, replicability, and cost-effectiveness of NWFP innovations. This involves developing methods to assess ecological and socio-economic impacts, identifying pathways for upscaling successful pilots, and ensuring that research outcomes are accessible to practitioners. Collaboration with Operational Groups is essential to bridge the gap between science and practice.

Operational Groups & producer organizations: OGs represent a unique interface between research, practice, and entrepreneurship. They can co-develop innovative business models adapted to local contexts, improve harvesting and processing techniques, and test new organizational arrangements that strengthen the bargaining power of small producers. By building networks across borders, they also facilitate learning and cooperation between regions with similar NWFP potential, creating the foundations for more resilient and competitive value chains.

Private sector: Companies and entrepreneurs can drive market development by investing in niche products, branding, and certification schemes. This is especially important to position European NWFPs competitively against international substitutes such as imported pine nuts or hydrocarbon-based resins. By engaging with sustainable supply chains, the private sector can also diversify its portfolio with bio-based materials that respond to growing consumer demand for natural, environmentally friendly products.

Civil society & consumers: Ultimately, the success of NWFP value chains also depends on societal demand and awareness. Consumers and community groups can support sustainable NWFPs through informed purchasing choices, participation in certification schemes, and engagement with local food and tourism markets. By valuing NWFPs not only as products but also as carriers of cultural heritage and biodiversity, civil society plays a crucial role in ensuring their long-term sustainability.

Policy implications

For NWFPs to fully realize their economic, ecological, and cultural potential, they must be structurally integrated into mainstream EU policies. Instruments such as the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), the EU Biodiversity Strategy, and the Farm-to-Fork Strategy already provide entry points, but stronger coherence and coordination are required. Looking ahead, the new EU Bioeconomy Strategy and the forthcoming Circular Economy Act will be decisive in supporting this vision, ensuring that NWFPs are recognized as key resources for a sustainable and innovative bio-based economy.

A critical aspect concerns funding. More flexible funding instruments are needed: longer project lifetimes, cascade funding mechanisms for local initiatives, and tailored tools for small-scale actors such as collectors and producer organizations. These measures would allow experiments to mature into stable business models and territorial value chains. Cross-border collaboration also plays a vital role. Transnational OGs, thematic networks, and structured exchange programs can accelerate the dissemination of knowledge, strengthen cooperation across regions, and help scale innovations beyond local contexts.

Another priority is strengthening transparency and data availability. Price observatories, digital traceability systems, and reliable statistics are essential tools to increase market visibility, attract investment, and build consumer trust in NWFPs. Finally, policies must also emphasize the social dimension. Improving labor conditions and empowering producer organizations are not only matters of equity but also crucial steps for building stable, fair, and competitive value chains. NWFPs are not only economic assets; they are also drivers of gender inclusion, rural employment, and the safeguarding of cultural heritage. By supporting these dimensions, innovation in NWFPs can contribute to more resilient rural communities and a fairer, more sustainable bioeconomy.

NON-WOOD FOREST PRODUCTS: Paving the way to a sustainable future in the EU

NWFP into EU Policies

- CAP
- EU biodiversity strategy
- Farm-to-Fork strategy
- Bioeconomy strategy
- Circular economy act
- Cascade funding
- Tailored for small-scale actors
- Stable business models

FLEXIBLE FUNDING

Longer project lifetimes

To set-up new business opportunities

- International Operational Groups
- Thematic networks
- Exchange programs
- Knowledge dissemination
- Regional cooperation

TRANSNATIONAL COLLABORATION

Better tools for small-scale

- Price observatories
- Digital traceability
- Reliable statistics
- Market visibility
- Consumer trust
- Attractive investments

TRANSPARENCY & DATA

- Traditional knowledge and practices protection
- Bridging the gap between people and forests

SOCIAL DIMENSION

Conclusions

Innovations in Non-Wood Forest Products (NWFPs) are vital to fully embed them in the bioeconomy, boosting rural development and human well-being. We must bridge science, practice, and policy to foster comprehensive technological and social innovations. This transition will elevate NWFPs from "invisible" status to central resources in Europe's bioeconomy, a future dependent on empowered local actors, cohesive policies, and strong international cooperation.

Policy briefs on
“Agroforestry systems”

CAP – Common Agriculture Policy (2023-2027)

Why innovations matter for agroforestry?

Increased knowledge and the development of innovations in the agroforestry sector provide farmers with tools to improve the management, production and marketing of their products, thereby enhancing the value of these systems. The results of the **Operational Groups** developed in the areas of nutrition, natural regeneration, networking, use of new information technologies, plant health, etc., have provided agroforestry farmers with a wealth of important information that can be implemented in their activities, while also promoting the adaptation of these systems to climate change.

Figure 1: Innovation types for agroforestry

Key statement

Agroforestry, especially in Southern European countries, is due to the use of space by human communities, which have developed agricultural and pastoral activities in wooded areas, creating a complex and multi-purpose system. These agroforestry systems are a good way to adapt to climate change, as they are more resilient to rising temperatures, torrential rain, and long periods of drought, while also promoting resistance to plant pests and diseases. In theory, the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) could be the best instrument for promoting agroforestry in Europe, and farmers who develop these systems should be rewarded for their efforts in building or maintaining agroforestry systems. This would be justified by the significance of these management and production systems, enhancing the social, economic and ecological resilience of vast areas in the EU, mainly in southern Europe.

However, the CAP needs to be reviewed and updated to encourage the development of existing agroforestry areas and the creation of new ones. Indeed, agroforestry systems, which are typical of Southern Europe, are now increasingly acknowledged and a matter of interest in Central and Northern Europe. Nevertheless, it is essential to retrieve their different characteristics according to the regions where agroforestry is (or can be) implemented. Implementing such systems faces the competition of extremely intensive agriculture or forestry and some misunderstanding about their features, primarily their mixed characteristics, which often do not fit into the conventional models in many regions.

Who can do what?

Agroforestry systems are probably the best way for farmers to adapt to climate change, due to the multi features the system gives, providing a complete basket of opportunity, namely provision of ecosystem services, different sources and periods of cash flows, better protection against diseases and plagues, as well as climate edges.

Farmers should try to establish agroforestry by planting trees or promoting natural regeneration in agricultural areas. This objective can be reached by clearing forest trees to a low-density system. Subsequently, activities should be combined, including agriculture, grazing, and forestry, either together or in a dualistic manner.

On the other hand, it should encourage the maintenance of existing agroforestry systems, increasing tree density, favouring natural tree regeneration and densification with new tree plantations. It is also essential to encourage a reduction in soil disturbance by increasing the period of disturbance or by using direct sowing when establishing crops or permanent grasslands. Farmers should look for the adaptation of livestock caring capacity to the characteristics of different agroforestry systems to optimise their use and prevent any damage that animals may cause.

CAP should encourage the establishment of new agroforestry areas, with different types and multiple species, favouring the introduction of species other than traditional ones.

CAP should also encourage the adaptation of livestock caring capacity to the characteristics of different agroforestry systems to optimise their use and prevent any damage that animals may cause. Finally, the CAP should reward farmers who achieve good results in their activity, encouraging everyone to manage their agroforestry holdings better and improve their incomes.

Policy implications

CAP regulations are designed for agriculture or forestry but can be adapted to agroforestry systems. Such adaptations create incompatibilities, however, due to the ineligibility of situations common in agricultural or forestry systems, such as double subsidies for controlling scrub in certain areas, excessive tree density and the management of shrubby or woody weeds. As an example, currently, CAP penalises the maintenance of agroforestry systems by not allowing high levels of shade, i.e. it does not allow high tree densities, which could improve the physical and chemical conditions of the soil and reduce soil erosion processes.

Farmers expect more CAP support, allowing the maintenance of these systems, with a greater capacity to adapt to climate change than pure agricultural systems, and with a greater capacity to produce ecosystem services, such as atmospheric carbon capture and sequestration, water and soil conservation, maintenance of biodiversity levels and maintenance of cultural values associated with these systems. At least, they expect not to be harmed, which often happens.

Conclusions

Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) is the preferred instrument for promoting the development of agroforestry areas, which are a very important system for counterbalancing the effects of climate change in Europe. It will have to focus on defining new support measures that enable the maintenance and development of new agroforestry areas, rewarding farmers who achieve good results for their work.

FOREST4EU

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About FOREST4EU

The key objective of FOREST4EU, funded by the Horizon Europe program, is to connect Operational Groups across Europe, fostering synergies and facilitating the exchange of best practices. The project is actively collecting and disseminating valuable information developed by these OGs, creating a central resource for the forestry community.

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